

Public Debt Forecasting in Kenya: Integrating Macroeconomic Variables with Arimax and Extreme Gradient Boosting

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 15 August 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Ndegwa Catherine Mure</p>	<p>In recent years, public debt in Kenya has been increasing rapidly, raising concerns about its sustainability and economic implications. As of July 2024, the public debt was roughly 10.6 trillion Ksh, reflecting a 2.9 percent increase from June 2023 when it stood at 10.3 trillion Ksh (Statista, 2024). This trend highlights the urgent need for accurate forecasting to ensure effective debt management and economic stability. This study aims to forecast Kenya’s public debt by comparing a statistical model (ARIMAX) and a machine learning model (XGBoost). Macroeconomic indicators i.e. GDP, inflation, exchange rate and interest rate, are incorporated to analyze their impact on debt trends and evaluate the predictive performance of both ARIMAX and XGBoost. Additionally, scenario simulation is employed to assess how varying economic conditions affect public debt trajectories. The decision to compare ARIMAX and XGBoost is based on their distinct strengths and modeling assumptions. ARIMAX is effective in capturing linear relationships and temporal dependencies, while XGBoost is capable of detecting complex non-linear interactions and hidden patterns in the data. By comparing these two methods, the study aims to evaluate their respective forecasting performance, understand the influence of macroeconomic indicators on public debt, and determine which approach provides more accurate and policy-relevant predictions under various economic scenarios. The study utilizes historical data from 2001 to 2023, obtained from the Central Bank of Kenya (CBK) and Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS). By integrating statistical modeling, machine learning, and scenario simulation, this research aims to provide a comprehensive forecasting framework to support policymakers in making informed decisions for sustainable debt management.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Public Debt, ARIMAX, XGBoost, Macroeconomic Indicators, Scenario Simulation, Kenya</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

Public debt accumulation has become a major concern for many developing countries including Kenya. In Kenya, it has significantly increased over time due to the need to source affordable loans with fewer risks. These loans are mainly used to finance development projects, public services, and infrastructure, but still, they can pose serious risks to the economy’s stability if not properly managed [1]. Public debt arises when tax revenues and income from other sources are lower than what the government spends [2]. Since the total income cannot compete with the ever-increasing government expenditure, this leads to public debt, both domestic and external. In Kenya, public debt is linked to macroeconomic factors such as GDP, inflation, exchange rate, and interest rate.

GDP indicates the overall performance of the economy. It measures the monetary value of final goods and services produced in a given period hence determining whether the country can generate revenue to service debt. Inflation is the rate of increase in prices over a given period. It influences the cost of living which in turn can affect fiscal policies and debt sustainability. Exchange rate is the rate at which one currency can be converted into another. It dictates how much of one currency you need to get a certain amount of another. Interest rate, on the other hand, is the percentage cost of borrowing money, paid to the lender. Countries with low growth rates and high inflation struggle to sustain debt leading to increased borrowing costs, fiscal crisis, and currency devaluation [3]. Depreciating exchange rate and rising interest rate increase the

burden of debt making repayment more challenging [4, 5]. Several studies have been employed to model and forecast public debt, with the most common methods being time series analysis and econometric models. ARIMA has been widely used due to its effectiveness in modeling temporal dependencies. Some studies have demonstrated the use of this model in analyzing debt trends and making policy recommendations [2, 6]. ARIMAX extends ARIMA by including macroeconomic factors and this makes it more suitable for forecasting public debt. However, this method may fail to capture non-linear relationships between the variables, especially in the context of economic shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic, recessions or structural changes. In recent years, machine learning techniques such as XGBoost and LSTM Networks have proven their ability to handle large datasets and non-linear relationships. These methods identify complex patterns and interactions in data that traditional statistical models may miss. For example, XGBoost has been used successfully for loan default prediction, offering high accuracy in identifying risky customers in financial data [7]. Despite the advances in forecasting methodologies, the role of macroeconomic variables in shaping public debt trajectories has yet to be comprehensively analyzed [6]. This study focuses on addressing these gaps that can provide policymakers with robust tools for sustainable debt management in Kenya. By comparing these 2 models on extensive historical debt in Kenya, the study aims to identify the optimal model for forecasting the nation's future debt.

II. RELATED WORKS

Various studies have used different methodologies to predict public debt trajectories, each with its strengths and limitations. ARIMA models have been used widely for time series forecasting. It was used in a study focusing on Ukraine's government debt to predict future debt values. Results showed that the model was effective in capturing trends and cyclic movements in debt accumulation making it reliable for short term forecasting. However, it was noted that the model couldn't effectively predict sudden economic shocks [8]. A comprehensive study on forecasting Kenya's public debt using both the ARIMA and Vector Autoregressive (VAR) models was conducted. The research demonstrated that while ARIMA was effective in modeling univariate debt series, VAR offered a more robust framework by incorporating multiple macroeconomic variables such as GDP growth, inflation, and interest rates. The study found that VAR models outperformed ARIMA in long-term forecasting due to their ability to reflect dynamic feedback among variables [9]. This supports the rationale for using models like ARIMAX or multivariate ML approaches, which can accommodate external macroeconomic factors and better capture economic complexity in public debt trends.

In another study, the influence of key macroeconomic indicators was explored, particularly inflation, fiscal deficits,

and exchange rate volatility, on the dynamics of public debt in Kenya. Although the work did not focus on forecasting, their findings are critical in identifying relevant variables that impact public debt. These macroeconomic drivers are useful for enhancing forecasting accuracy, particularly in models like ARIMAX and XGBoost that allow the integration of exogenous predictors. The study underlines the need for more sophisticated forecasting models that reflect the influence of fiscal and monetary indicators on debt evolution [10]. ARIMA and Holt-Winters models were used in a comparative study to forecast Kenya's public debt where both models provided accurate short-term forecasts with Holt-Winters performing better when seasonality was present in the data. However, ARIMA was more effective in longterm trend estimation. From findings, the model assumed that past patterns would continue, making it ineffective for handling irregular economic shocks. The interpretability of machine learning models has been a growing concern, especially in policymaking environments [6].

Machine learning applications emphasized the importance of explainability, particularly when used in sensitive public domains like finance. There is need for a balance between predictive performance and model transparency, supporting the use of ARIMA or ARIMAX for their clarity while leveraging the predictive power of models like XGBoost where high accuracy is critical [11]. Techniques such as XGBoost and LSTM have been applied widely in financial forecasting but there is limited research on their application in public debt forecasting. However, a study on U.S treasury interest rate forecasting demonstrated their effectiveness. From the study XGBoost handled complex, non-linear relationships therefore outperformed traditional econometric models in predicting interest rate. LSTM networks on the other hand were found to be effective for long term sequence prediction [12].

The results from a study investigating the effectiveness of XGBoost and LSTM, showed that XGBoost achieved a Directional Accuracy Percentage (DAP) of 71.02% while LSTM had a DAP ranging from 62.42% to 67.10%. This shows that XGBoost was more effective, further demonstrating its predictive strength. These findings suggest that XGBoost could offer similar advantages in public debt forecasting, especially when macroeconomic volatility is a factor [13]. ARIMAX model was used to forecast inflation in Kenya and found that including external factors such as oil prices and exchange rates improved model performance compared to traditional ARIMA [14]. These findings are especially relevant to this study, as they confirm that ARIMAX models offer greater flexibility and accuracy in forecasting economic indicators influenced by external shocks. The success of ARIMAX in macroeconomic forecasting reinforces its applicability to public debt modeling, particularly in contexts where debt is sensitive to global and domestic economic fluctuations.

A study on domestic credit growth using seasonal ARIMA . The study found that ARIMA could effectively capture both trend and seasonal cycles. The forecast projected a steady growth rate in domestic credit into 2024, validating ARIMA’s role in stable financial environments [15]. This highlights ARIMA’s utility but also suggests limitations in handling structural shifts or non linear macroeconomic influences, areas where models like XGBoost may provide an edge. Another study demonstrated that XGBoost significantly outperformed ARIMA and SARIMA, in predicting inflation in Indonesia. The model reduced RMSE by approximately 45%, highlighting its strength in capturing non linear dependencies and structural shifts in macroeconomic data [16]. This supports the role of XGBoost in macroeconomic forecasting where sudden changes in policy or global markets may disrupt historical trends. Hybrid models have also been implemented where a hybrid Long Short Term Memory (LSTM)-ARIMA approach was used to forecast equity indices and optimize algorithmic trading strategies [17]. CNN-LSTM-XGBoost model has also been used for stock price prediction, noting strong performance in volatile environments [18]. Their findings validate XGBoost’s value when used as a comparative benchmark due to its reliable predictive performance across multiple metrics.

In terms of macroeconomic indicators, an ARIMA(2,2,2) model has been used to forecast inflation trends in Kenya using historical CPI data. The model achieved low root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE), confirming its effectiveness in modeling macroeconomic variables with strong autocorrelation structures. Nonetheless, the study acknowledged that ARIMA may underperform during periods of economic instability or sudden fiscal shocks, emphasizing the importance of incorporating exogenous variables, which ARIMAX can accommodate [19]. The performance of XGBoost with other ensemble learners such as Random Forest and traditional Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM) was evaluated. The study evaluated over 100 datasets and found that XGBoost generally achieved higher accuracy. The authors of this study emphasized XGBoost’s robustness in handling missing data, multicollinearity, and noisy features, making it ideal for economic forecasting tasks where data imperfections are common [20].

This research analyzes both ARIMAX and XGBoost models through public debt forecasting. By comparing these 2 powerful models, this study identifies the optimal model for effectively and accurately forecasting Kenya’s public debt.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodological framework used to forecast Kenya’s public debt. A comparative and predictive research approach integrating statistical (ARIMAX) and Machine Learning (XGBoost) techniques were employed while incorporating GDP, Inflation, Exchange and Interest rates as the key macroeconomic indicators. Scenario

simulation was also incorporated to assess the impact of varying economic conditions on debt sustainability.

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

The public debt data used span from 2001-2023 and was obtained from the Central Bank of Kenya (CBK) website. The dataset underwent standard time series preprocessing and explanatory analysis using Python programming language. Techniques like linear interpolation to handle missing data, handling outliers, smoothing and stationarity were performed.

B. Model Selection and Implementation

With the pre-processed data, both ARIMAX and XGBoost models were trained and evaluated to determine the optimal forecasting approach. The selection of the best ARIMAX configuration was guided by Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). Hyperparameter tuning was performed for XGBoost using grid search cross validation to optimize parameters such as learning rate, tree depth, and the number of estimators.

C. Model Specification

1) ARIMAX Model:

ARIMAX model extends the ARIMA framework by incorporating exogenous variables, to improve forecasting accuracy. It is a multiple Linear Regression Model denoted by the ARIMAX(p, d, q) i.e. Autoregressive (AR) term [p], Differencing [d], and Moving Average (MA) [q]. The general form of the ARIMAX model incorporating autoregressive (AR), integrated (I), and moving average (MA) components along with exogenous variables is given as:

$$\Delta^d y_t = c + \sum_{i=1}^p \phi_i \Delta^d y_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^q \theta_j \varepsilon_{t-j} + \sum_{k=1}^m \beta_k x_{k,t} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta^d y_t$ is the d^{th} order differenced target variable, c is the constant term, p is the number of autoregressive lags with coefficients ϕ_i , q is the number of moving average terms with coefficients θ_j , $x_{k,t}$ represents the k^{th} exogenous variable at time t , m is the number of exogenous variables, β_k are the coefficients for the exogenous variables and, ε_t is the white noise error term.

ARIMAX relies on the following assumptions:

- I. The time series must be stationary, meaning the mean and variance remain constant over time.
- II. The model assumes a linear relationship between the dependent variable and its past values.
- III. Independence of residuals i.e., the error terms should not exhibit autocorrelation.

After fitting the model to the data and estimating parameters, residual diagnostics test was performed on the fitted model. The Residual Vs Fitted values, Histogram of residuals, and the Ljung Box test were applied to test for the models’ assumptions.

2) *Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost):*

XGBoost is a supervised learning algorithm based on gradient boosting trees and per research, it has shown exceptional performance in predictive tasks [21]. This machine learning technique is known for its ensemble learning approach and capability to handle structured data. XGBoost operates within the gradient boosting framework which focuses on optimizing speed and model performance. XGBoost incorporates L1 (Lasso) and L2 (Ridge) regularization techniques which prevent overfitting tendencies [13]. It is defined as:

$$\hat{y}_i = \sum_{k=1}^K f_k(x_i), \quad f_k \in F \quad (2)$$

where \hat{y}_i is the predicted public debt at time i , $f_k(x_i)$ represents each decision tree, k is the number of boosting iterations, f is the set of regression trees, F is the space of regression trees used for boosting.

The objective function minimizes the loss function while applying regularization

$$obj_j = \sum_{i=1}^n l(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{k=1}^K \Omega(f_k) \quad (3)$$

The regularization function $\Omega(f_k)$ used to penalize model complexity is given by:

$$\Omega(f_k) = \frac{1}{2} \lambda \sum_{j=1}^{T_k} w_{kj}^2 + \alpha \sum_{j=1}^{T_k} |w_{kj}| \quad (4)$$

where $l(y_i, \hat{y}_i)$ is the loss function measuring prediction error, $\Omega(f_k)$ is the regularization term that prevents overfitting. Grid SearchCV was used to systematically test different combinations of hyperparameters and select the best-performing set based on evaluation metrics such as RMSE, MAPE, and R^2 .

D. Variable Importance and Selection

For the ARIMAX model, importance was evaluated based on the statistical significance (p values) and magnitude of the model coefficients. Variables with low p-values (less than 0.05) and larger coefficients were considered more influential in explaining changes in public debt over time. For the XGBoost model, variable importance was assessed using feature importance metrics, which measured the contribution of each variable to the predictive accuracy of the model. Variables that showed consistently high importance across both models were interpreted as having strong economic influence on public debt.

E. Performance Evaluation

To assess the reliability and performance of both models, evaluation was performed using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), and R^2 Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) was used to measure the average prediction error.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (5)$$

where n is the number of observations / data points, y_i is the actual public debt value at time i , \hat{y}_i is the predicted public debt value at time i . Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) expresses forecast error as a percentage of actual values.

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100 \quad (6)$$

where n is the number of observations, y_i is the actual public debt at time i , \hat{y}_i is the predicted public debt value at time i . R-squared score measured how well the models explained variability in public debt.

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (7)$$

The model with the lowest RMSE and MAPE, and the highest R^2 was considered the most accurate forecasting method.

F. Scenario Simulation

This is an essential technique in forecasting, that helps policymakers to explore how public debt might evolve under different macroeconomic scenarios. Three scenarios were evaluated: the **Baseline Scenario**, which assumes that GDP, inflation, interest rates, and exchange have no major disruptions; the **Optimistic Scenario**, assumes accelerated GDP growth, stabilized or declining inflation, and constant interest and exchange rates, and the **Pessimistic Scenario**, which assumes slowing GDP growth and rising inflation. Both ARIMAX and XGBoost models were trained on historical data and used to forecast public debt under these simulated conditions by adjusting macroeconomic variables accordingly. The resulting forecasts were compared using key indicators such as the debt-to-GDP ratio, debt-to-interest rate, and debt-to-exchange rate.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

G. Checking for Stationarity

The original Public Debt data was tested for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. The results showed a high p-value of 0.976 indicating non-stationarity therefore,

second order differencing was done to achieve stationarity using the .diff() function in Python as shown in figure 1. Differencing is a technique in time series that helps to transform non-stationary data into a stationary form to stabilize mean and eliminate trends [22].

Figure 1: Differenced Total Debt over Time

H. ARIMAX Model Implementation

An exhaustive Grid Search was conducted to identify the best fitting ARIMAX model with a training set which was 80 percent (2001-2019) of the data. The search explored various combinations of the (p, d, q) parameters. Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) was used to evaluate the model’s performance. The best fitted model had an order of (1,2,2) with first order autoregressive process, second order differencing, and second order moving average and an AIC value of 4663.86. Substituting these values of the optimal model in equation (1) gives:

$$\Delta^2 y_t = c + \phi_1 \Delta^2 y_{t-1} + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} + \sum_{i=1}^4 \beta_i x_{i,t} + \epsilon_t \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta^2 y_t$ is the second differenced public debt at time t , c is a constant term, ϕ_1 is the autoregressive coefficient of order 1, θ_1, θ_2 are the moving average coefficients of orders 1 and 2 respectively, $x_{i,t}$ for $i = 1, \dots, 4$ are the exogenous macroeconomic variables, β_i are the coefficients corresponding to each exogenous variable, and ϵ_t is the white noise error term at time t .

I. XGBoost Model Fitting

Lag features were introduced to enable XGBoost to learn from temporal dependencies in the data. Each macroeconomic variable and the target variable, Public Debt, were shifted by one time step (i.e. one year) to create lagged versions. The use of lagged inputs helps to incorporate time-series dynamics into machine learning models like XGBoost, [21]. To optimize the performance of the XGBoost model, a combination of GridSearch and TimeSeriesSplit with 5-fold cross-validation was conducted over a range of hyperparameters. The optimal set of hyperparameters were:- Number of Observations 263, Number of Estimators: 300, Learning Rate: 0.01, Max. depth of trees: 3, L1 regularization term: 0.5, and L2 regularization term: 0.5. This set was used

to train the final XGBoost model on the full training dataset which was 80% of the data (2001-2019).

The predicted public debt at time t , denoted by \hat{y}_t , is given by the sum of outputs from 300 additive regression trees. Substituting equation (2) with $K = 300$ gives:

$$\hat{y}_t = \sum_{k=1}^{300} f_k(\mathbf{x}_i), \quad f_k \in \mathcal{F} \quad (9)$$

The objective function minimised:

$$\text{Obj} = \sum_{i=1}^{263} l(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{k=1}^{300} \Omega(f_k) \quad (10)$$

The regularization term, $\Omega(f_k)$ in (9), penalizes the complexity of each individual tree and is defined as:

$$\Omega(f_k) = \frac{1}{2} \lambda \sum_{j=1}^{T_k} w_{kj}^2 + \alpha \sum_{j=1}^{T_k} |w_{kj}| \quad (11)$$

Therefore, substituting (10) in (9) gives:

$$\text{Obj} = \sum_{i=1}^{263} l(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{k=1}^{300} \left(\frac{1}{2} \times 0.5 \sum_{j=1}^{T_k} w_{kj}^2 + 0.5 \sum_{j=1}^{T_k} |w_{kj}| \right) \quad (12)$$

where y_i is the actual public debt at time i , \hat{y}_i is the predicted public debt at time i , f_k represents the k^{th} regression tree in the ensemble, x_i is the vector of exogenous macroeconomic variables at time i , T_k is the number of leaves in tree k , w_{kj} is the score on leaf j of tree k , λ and α are the L2 (Ridge) and L1 (Lasso) regularization parameters, respectively. The hyperparameters include learning rate $\eta = 0.01$, max depth $d = 3$, column subsample 0.9, and subsample 0.7, and the gamma parameter $\gamma = 0$ indicates no additional penalty on the number of leaves.

J. Influence of Macroeconomic Variables on Public Debt

This study evaluated the relative influence of macroeconomic indicators i.e. GDP, inflation, exchange rate, and interest rate, on Kenya’s public debt. Figure 2 shows the feature importance derived from the XGBoost model.

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Figure 2: Feature importance from XGBoost model

Table 1 presents the ARIMAX model results. Interest rate had a statistically significant negative relationship with public debt (coefficient = -16,340; p-value = 0.001). In contrast, GDP has a small but statistically significant positive effect (coefficient = 0.0128; p = 0.021). Inflation Rate and Exchange Rate were not statistically significant $p > 0.05$, indicating weak influence.

Table 1: ARIMAX Model Coefficients for Exogenous Variables

Variable	Coefficient	p-value	Significance
Exchange Rate	64.93	0.896	Not Significant
Inflation	1040.01	0.751	Not Significant
GDP	0.128	0.021	Significant
Interest Rate	-16,340	0.001	Significant

K. Determining the Optimal Model for Forecasting Kenya’s Public Debt

The ARIMAX and XGBoost models were compared to determine the most effective model to forecast public debt in Kenya using GDP, Inflation, Interest Rate and Exchange Rate as macroeconomic variables. Forecasting for both models was done for a period of 4 years (i.e. 2020-2023). The performance of each model was evaluated based on visual inspection of the predicted and actual debt trajectories and accuracy measures such as Mean Absolute Percentage Error(MAPE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and R-Squared were used to compare the forecasting accuracy for each model.

L. Comparative evaluation of both ARIMAX and XGBoost Models

Figure 3: Actual Vs Predicted Public Debt (ARIMAX and XGBoost With Macroeconomic Variables)

As seen on Figure 3, the 2 models capture the upward trend of the actual public debt. The red line representing XGBoost predictions appears to track the actual public debt (blue line) more closely than the ARIMAX predictions. The model demonstrates a superior ability to capture underlying patterns and turning points in the actual public debt. The green line representing ARIMAX predictions also appears to be capturing the general upward trend but is less responsive to the dynamic changes in the rate of debt accumulation and tends to lag behind the actual public debt. The ARIMAX model struggles to fully capture the nonlinear accelerations in debt accumulation.

Based on accuracy measures, XGBoost had a lower RMSE value of 556,672.24 compared to ARIMAX’s 1,030,374.56 confirming that on average, its predictions are more accurate than ARIMAX. XGBoost’s MAPE value was 4.84% while ARIMAX had 9.52% showing its predictions are more accurate in percentage terms. The R^2 value was 0.86 compared to ARIMAX’s 0.51 suggesting that XGBoost explains a much larger portion of the variability in the actual public debt.

M. Future Predictions for ARIMAX and XGBoost Optimal Models

Figure 4 illustrates the future projections of Kenya’s total public debt from 2024 to 2028 using the optimal ARIMAX and XGBoost models, alongside the historical trend.

Figure 4: Future Predictions plot for XGBoost and ARIMAX Optimal models

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For the subsequent 5 year forecast, both models were retrained on the entire historical. This retraining process is standard in time series forecasting and ensures that the models incorporate the most recent information to produce more robust forward-looking estimates [23]. After retraining, both models generated future projections (solid lines) that diverged noticeably from their earlier test predictions.

Table 2: Forecasted Public Debt in Kenya using ARIMAX and XGBoost

Year	ARIMAX (Million KSH)	XGBoost (Million Ksh)
2024	136.98	140.30
2025	151.21	158.53
2026	165.90	175.87
2027	180.44	194.02
2028	195.02	211.97

N. Scenario Simulation

The graphs below show the simulation of public debt, debt-to-GDP, debt-to-Exchange Rate (XGBoost), and debt-to-Interest Rate (ARIMAX) under Baseline, Optimistic, and Pessimistic scenarios. The 3 scenarios incorporated assumptions about macroeconomic trends. They were modeled using a combination of linear and compound growth approaches, and adjusted using model specific amplification factors based on variable importance. The forecasting horizon extends for 5 years from the last observed data point, with each forecasted variable initialized using its final historical value. These served as baseline reference points for forward projections under each scenario. To introduce structural variability over time, the 5 year forecast horizon was split into two equal phases. This phased structure allowed for piecemeal changes, where macroeconomic indicators evolved differently across the two sub-periods, thus capturing potential mid-horizon shifts in the economic environment.

Table 3: Forecasted Total Public Debt under Different Scenarios

Model	Baseline Scenario	Optimistic Scenario	Pessimistic Scenario
XGBoost	13,987,372.54	13,776,184.49	13,954,764.39
ARIMA X	12,182,814.66	12,139,780.18	12,113,112.34

Table 4: Forecasted Debt-to-GDP Ratio under different Scenarios

Model	Baseline Scenario	Optimistic Scenario	Pessimistic Scenario
XGBoost	84.16%	81.81%	91.22%
ARIMAX	73.30%	75.58%	79.18%

Table 5: Forecasted Debt-to-Interest Rate Ratio (ARIMAX) under Different Scenario

Model	Baseline Scenario	Optimistic Scenario	Pessimistic Scenario
ARIMAX	893,823.53	890,666.19	774,991.19

Table 6: Forecasted Debt-to- Exchange Rate Ratio (XGBoost) under Different Scenarios

Model	Baseline Scenario	Optimistic Scenario	Pessimistic Scenario
XGBoost	89,777.02	91,133.77	87,241.30

Figure 5: XGBoost Debt-to-Exchange Rate Ratio

Figure 6: XGBoost Debt-to-GDP Ratio

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Figure 7: XGBoost Total Debt Scenarios

Figure 8: ARIMAX Debt-to-Interest Rate Ratio

Figure 9: ARIMAX Debt-to-GDP Ratio

Figure 10: ARIMAX Total Debt Scenarios

The relatively minor differences across the total debt scenarios imply that neither model anticipates drastic shifts in public debt accumulation in response to the simulated macroeconomic paths. A possible explanation is that the compounding or linear changes introduced in the exogenous variables, even when amplified, may have been too moderate to elicit large variations in public debt.

The debt-to-interest rate ratio under the ARIMAX model, contrary to expectation, showed the lowest ratio under the Pessimistic Scenario, at approximately 774,991, compared to 893,823 in the Baseline and 890,666 in the Optimistic case. It is generally expected for this ratio to rise under pessimistic conditions due to increasing debt and higher interest rates. However, the result is mathematically justified when considering the structure of the ratio. A similar explanation applies to the debt-to-exchange rate ratio in XGBoost. The lowest ratio is observed under the Pessimistic Scenario 87,241, while the highest is under the Optimistic Scenario 91,133.

O. Discussion

This study revealed notable differences in forecasting performance between ARIMAX and XGBoost when applied to Kenya’s public debt data. XGBoost consistently outperformed ARIMAX across all metrics, achieving a MAPE of 4.84% and $R^2=0.86$, compared to ARIMAX’s MAPE of 9.52% and $R^2=0.51$. The weaker performance of ARIMAX reflects the limitations of linear models in capturing nonlinear relationships and structural changes common in macroeconomic data [24]. Similar findings have been reported where findings showed that machine learning methods like XGBoost and Random Forests outperform traditional statistical models in complex time series forecasting [23, 25].

While XGBoost provided superior predictive performance, ARIMAX remains valuable for policy analysis because of its interpretability and ability to quantify the impact of independent variables [26]. In this study, ARIMAX indicated a significant negative effect of interest rates on public debt, consistent with previous studies [27], whereas XGBoost identified exchange rate as the most influential factor, supporting that currency depreciation raises debt servicing costs, driving further borrowing needs [28, 29].

When used for future predictions, ARIMAX produced an exponential growth trajectory for public debt, indicating compounding effects of lagged debt and macroeconomic variables under worsening trends. Conversely, XGBoost forecasted a more conservative linear growth path, reflecting its ability to generalize patterns and smooth out short-term volatility due to its regularization and tree-based structure. Exchange rate influence, identified as most important by XGBoost’s feature analysis, further shaped its projections, aligning with studies that emphasized the exchange rate’s critical role in debt servicing and fiscal sustainability [30].

These differences between the models highlight how underlying assumptions affect forecasts, ARIMAX indicates a higher risk of debt escalation, while XGBoost projects steady but controlled growth, offering valuable input for scenario-based policy planning.

In scenario simulation, both models provided contrasting yet insightful outcomes. XGBoost projected sharp increases in total debt and debt-to-GDP ratio across all scenarios, exceeding 80%, signaling potential debt distress if current trends persist. According to studies, developing economies should maintain this ratio below 60% to avoid fiscal risks, suggesting Kenya may face heightened debt sustainability challenges [30]. However, XGBoost’s sensitivity to recent data patterns, while enhancing performance, can also make it prone to overfitting in volatile environments. ARIMAX, produced more restrained forecasts with declining debt-to-GDP ratios across all scenarios. Its emphasis on lagged relationships and structural dynamics offers more stability and interpretability for economic policy-making [31]. Interestingly, the debt-to-interest and debt-to-exchange rate ratios declined in the pessimistic scenario because both denominators were assumed to rise, illustrating the need for careful interpretation of ratio-based indicators when scenario assumptions shift significantly.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the forecasting of Kenya’s public debt using two distinct modeling approaches, ARIMAX and XGBoost, based on annual macroeconomic data from 2001 to 2023. The models incorporated GDP, inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates as predictors of public debt trends. The ARIMAX model offered strong interpretability and revealed statistically significant linear relationships, aligning well with traditional econometric expectations [25]. Conversely, the XGBoost model demonstrated superior predictive accuracy, leveraging its strength in capturing nonlinear relationships and handling multicollinearity common challenges in macroeconomic data [28]. Model performance was evaluated using RMSE, MAPE, and R^2 , with XGBoost outperforming ARIMAX in nearly all metrics. However, the trade-off between interpretability and accuracy was evident, while ARIMAX’s transparency is beneficial for policy interpretation and causal inference, XGBoost’s black-box nature necessitates the use of post-hoc interpretability tools for policy use. Variable importance results also varied. ARIMAX found GDP and interest rates to be most significant, while XGBoost identified inflation and exchange rate as primary drivers, indicating that each model provides unique insights based on its structural assumptions. Scenario-based forecasting was employed to assess model responsiveness under different macroeconomic conditions, baseline, optimistic, and pessimistic. Under all scenarios, XGBoost projected a higher debt-to-GDP ratio than ARIMAX, in some instances surpassing the IMF’s 60%

sustainability threshold [30]. While the pessimistic scenario forecasted increased debt burden and reduced fiscal space, the optimistic scenario demonstrated the benefits of accelerated GDP growth and inflation stabilization in maintaining debt sustainability. These findings align with research that emphasized the macroeconomic drivers of public debt in developing countries [27].

The scenario simulation underscored the value of combining data-driven models with policy-based scenarios to guide fiscal planning. Both models proved useful in stress testing Kenya’s public debt outlook, highlighting potential vulnerabilities and informing debt management strategies. The ARIMAX model’s structured form enables clear communication to policymakers, while XGBoost’s predictive strength supports proactive planning under uncertainty, [32, 33].

Based on the findings, several policy recommendations emerge. First, a hybrid modeling framework is advisable leveraging the interpretability of ARIMAX for explanatory insights and the predictive accuracy of XGBoost for forecasting. Second, maintaining macroeconomic stability, especially around exchange rates and inflation, is essential given their demonstrated influence on public debt. Third, institutionalizing scenario-based forecasting within national fiscal frameworks can improve preparedness and resilience in response to economic shocks.

Future research could enhance model accuracy and robustness by incorporating additional macroeconomic and political risk variables, experimenting with other machine learning models like LSTM and Random Forest, and applying interpretability methods such as SHAP or LIME. Furthermore, assessing model performance during periods of structural change or global crises would provide more resilient tools for public debt forecasting in volatile environments.

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